

ARIMA FORECASTING OF COVID-19 IN MINDANAO: EVALUATING THE EFFECTS OF TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY

Billy Bert K. Baitus III, Abdollah Adnan G. Dimaudtang, Raffaello T. Ravanera
and Jonathan A. Madronero

*Philippine Science High School - SOCCSKSARGEN Region Campus,
Brgy. Paraiso, Koronadal City, South Cotabato, Philippines*

ABSTRACT

Assessing the effect of meteorological factors on COVID-19 cases can help to understand the transmission patterns of the virus and provide valuable insights for public health interventions. This study assesses and forecasts the impact of daily temperature and humidity on COVID-19 cases across Mindanao. All regions of Mindanao's COVID-19 models' performance were compared. This study used the best-fit model to evaluate the regions: Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) modeling in R. ARIMA modeling is an effective method for analyzing and forecasting the COVID-19 outbreak. The findings showed a predicted slight increase and positive correlation in COVID-19 instances for regions 9 and 10. Moreover, there is a negative correlation between Regions 11, 12, 13, and BARMM and forecast stability around zero cases. Furthermore, the study examines a connection between the peaks and troughs in COVID-19 cases in Mindanao and temperature and humidity. Regional ARIMA models help decision-makers make well-informed choices, distribute resources wisely, and control the spread of the infection.

Keywords: *ARIMA, COVID-19, Humidity, Mindanao, Temperature*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, has profoundly impacted public health worldwide since its emergence in December 2019. In the

Philippines, as of January 8, 2024, there were 4,140,383 recorded cases. The pandemic has affected various sectors, including accountants in Mindanao, whose salaries have been adversely affected, and fishers in Davao Gulf, facing increased financial burdens and emotional strain, impacting their children's education (Enriquez et al., 2023; Macusi et al., 2022).

Research suggests that local air humidity and temperature play significant roles in COVID-19 mortality rates, with higher humidity and warmer temperatures potentially reducing transmission (Biktasheva, 2020; Gupta et al., 2020). Like other seasonal respiratory viruses, COVID-19 spreads more readily in cold and temperate regions. Studies also indicate that wind speed and temperature influence the spread of the virus, particularly during mealtimes and periods of high mobility (Ganslmeier et al., 2021).

Moreover, forecasting pandemics using Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) modeling shows promise for short-term predictions, although the accuracy diminishes over time. While initial forecasts align closely with actual values, long-term predictions become less reliable (Ospina et al., 2023).

This study investigates the correlation between COVID-19 cases and meteorological factors, specifically temperature and humidity. Drawing on Biktasheva's (2020) findings, which suggest a negative correlation between local air humidity and COVID-19 mortality, and Gupta et al.'s (2020) observations of an optimal absolute humidity range for COVID-19 transmission, this research aims to identify similar patterns in the Philippines, particularly in Mindanao. Understanding these relationships could provide valuable insights for future research and interventions aimed at mitigating the impact of the virus.

Research Questions

This research explores the intricate relationship between geographical factors, climatic conditions, and the spread of COVID-19 in Mindanao.

Specifically, it seeks to apply the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model to quantify the influence of regional geographical factors on the correlation between temperature, humidity, and COVID-19 cases.

1. How does the ARIMA model quantify the influence of regional geographical factors on the correlation between temperature, humidity, and COVID-19 cases in Mindanao?
2. Using the ARIMA model, what are the observed and forecasted trends of COVID-19 cases in Mindanao, and how can these insights inform future pandemic preparedness and response efforts?

METHODOLOGY

The data collection process for this study involved sourcing COVID-19 case data from March 2020 to December 2022 from the Department of Health's daily reports across various regions in Mindanao, alongside acquiring data on average daily temperature and humidity from PAGASA (Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration). Subsequently, data cleaning procedures were implemented to ensure data accuracy and reliability, including addressing missing values through mean imputation and considering outliers.

Data presentation encompassed textual, tabular, and graphical formats, employing line graphs to visualize the association between temperature and anticipated COVID-19 cases. At the same time, statistical treatments involved computing correlations and employing ARIMA models, leveraging R programming for data analysis (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2018). The ARIMA models were tailored to each region, integrating temperature and humidity data as external regressors, with forecasted COVID-19 cases plotted to provide insights into future trends, aiding in informed decision-making for public health strategies (Braun & Murdoch, 2021; Frost, 2023).

RESULTS

Region	ARIMA Model	RMSE	AICc	BIC
9	(3,0,1)	38.35	8,650.50	8,688.31
10	(5,0,3)	53.06	9,211.27	9,263.18
11	(5,1,4)	96.57	10,211.25	10,267.83
12	(2,1,4)	62.97	9,486.22	9,528.73
13	(2,1,3)	57.58	9,331.57	9,369.37
BARMM	(2,1,3)	20.66	7,586.46	7,624.26

Table 1. ARIMA Model for Each Region

Figure 1. Region 9 Forecast Plot.

Figure 2. Region 10 Forecast Plot.

Figure 3. Region 11 Forecast Plot.

Figure 4. Region 12 Forecast Plot.

Figure 5. *Region 13 Forecast Plot.*

Figure 6. *Region BARMM Forecast Plot.*

DISCUSSION

The quantities of the correlation coefficients of the COVID-19 cases and temperature range from 0.024 to 0.279, while the correlation coefficients between the COVID-19 cases and humidity range from 0.021 to 0.122. Additionally, only Region 10 has a positive r value for the COVID-19 cases and temperature, while only regions 10 and 13 have a negative r value for the COVID-19 cases and humidity.

The correlation between COVID-19 cases and meteorological factors varies across regions, with coefficient magnitudes ranging from 0.02 to 0.28, which matches the range of the r values from the meta-analysis of Islam and Noor (2022). Most regions showed a

negative correlation between the number of cases and temperature, except for Region 10. Conversely, most regions except Regions 10 and 13 have a positive correlation between the number of cases and humidity. This suggests that the number of COVID-19 cases tends to increase with decreasing temperature and increasing humidity for most regions.

The model shown in Table 4.2 is identified as an "ARIMA(p,d,q)" model, where 'p' signifies the count of autoregressive terms, 'd' represents the number of nonseasonal differences required to achieve stationarity, and 'q' denotes the quantity of lagged forecast errors in the prediction equation (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2018).

The three parameters of ARIMA models indicate the number of autoregressive terms, the number of differencing performed, and the number of lagged forecast errors. The autoregressive term p implies that the forecasted data regresses on its p-lagged values. This means that the forecasted values regress on their past five values in regions 10 and 11, while they regress on their past two values in regions 12, 13, and BARMM.

The integrated model d refers to the differencing performed for stationarity of a time series. A stationary time series is when the mean and variance are constant. Having a zero value on regions 9 and 10's integrated model implies that no differencing was performed for the regions, which means that regions 9 and 10's time series are already stationary. This also suggests that the time series for regions 9 and 10 show no predictable trends and seasonality. Meanwhile, regions 11, 12, 13, and BARMM had values of 1 for their degree of differencing. This implies that one differencing was to be performed for their time series to achieve stationarity.

The moving average model q is the quantity of lagged forecast errors in the model. Instead of using lagged values, it uses q-lagged errors. The moving average shows that the regression error linearly combines error terms whose values occurred contemporaneously and at various times in the past. The q values incorporate the dependency between an observation and a residual error from a moving average model applied to lagged observations. Regions 11 and 12 show more lagged forecast errors in the prediction equation of 4 points.

The trend of the forecasted values differs for each region. In regions 9 and 10, the values were observed to increase in the latter parts of 2022 and early parts of 2023 and then proceed with no fluctuations in the succeeding days. In regions 11, 12, 13, and BARMM, the forecasted values were observed to have a stable progression.

The observed difference in each region's forecasted values' trend behaviors might be caused by the difference in their ARIMA models' parameters, where regions 9 and 10 have zero values for their integrated model. The ranges of the forecasted values were observed not to exceed 20. In regions 9 and 10, the cases are expected to increase gradually in the succeeding years, while less than 20 to no cases are expected in regions 11, 12, 13, and BARMM.

Conclusions

The data on COVID-19 cases signified the highest number of cases during the first and third quarters of 2020-2022 and the lowest during the first quarter. A steady decrease in cases was definite from the fourth quarter until now.

The relationship between temperature and the COVID-19 cases is more likely negative, while the relationship between humidity and the COVID-19 cases is more likely positive. It only exhibited a positive correlation between temperature and the number of cases in Region 10 and a negative correlation between humidity and the number of cases in regions 10 and 13, which are the northern parts of Mindanao. The geographical location of each region might have contributed to the correlation between the variables.

The trend of the forecasted values differs for each region. In regions 9 and 10, the values were observed to increase in the latter parts of 2022 and early parts of 2023 and then proceed with no fluctuations in the succeeding days. As for the remaining regions, the forecasted values were observed to have a stable progression. The ranges of the forecasted values were observed to be at most 20. In regions 9 and 10, the cases are expected to increase gradually in the succeeding years, while less than 20 to no cases are expected in the other regions.

Recommendations

In obtaining the data, this study recommends that future researchers ask government agencies directly through a letter for faster data collection. It also advised immediate data cleaning upon receiving or collecting the data for it to be validated to reduce the risk of complications during the implementation of other tasks regarding the study.

This study also recommends considering other meteorological factors, such as rainfall, air pressure, and solar radiation, which may also relate to COVID-19 cases.

Using other statistical software, such as premium software, may also influence the data treatment and analysis of such a study. Other software may offer a quicker, easier, and more in-depth data review. However, R is the most recommended statistical software for forecasting because of its popularity, utility, accessibility, and ease of use.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Strict adherence to ethical guidelines was followed during the study. Data on temperature and humidity were obtained from PAG-ASA, while COVID-19 data came

from the DOH website. Although human participation was not directly involved, measures were taken to ensure data privacy. Proper permissions were secured for data access, and transparency was maintained regarding sources and limitations.

The research was conducted with integrity, avoiding conflicts of interest and ensuring objective analysis. Adherence to institutional and regulatory guidelines was upheld, and ethical considerations were integrated into data analysis. The broader implications for public health and policy were carefully considered. These efforts ensure that the research contributes valuable insights while upholding ethical standards.

Acknowledgments

The researchers would like to express their heartfelt gratitude to all individuals who supported and assisted them throughout their research. Furthermore, the researchers would also like to acknowledge CAD PAG-ASA for providing the dataset required for this study.

REFERENCES

- Biktasheva, I. V. (2020). Role of a habitat's air humidity in COVID-19 mortality. *Science of the Total Environment*, p. 736, 138763. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138763>
- Enriquez, K. O., Murcia, J. V., & Delima, A. J. P. (2023). *The case of employed accountants in Mindanao: Effect of COVID-19 pandemic on salary*. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*, 10(2), 202–209. <https://doi.org/10.21833/ijaas.2023.02.024>
- Ganslmeier, M., Furceri, D., & Ostry, J. D. (2021). *The impact of weather on the COVID-19 pandemic*. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-01189-3>
- Gupta, S., Raghuwanshi, G. S., & Chanda, A. (2020). Effect of weather on COVID-19 spread in the US: A prediction model for India in 2020. *Science of the Total Environment*, 728, 138860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138860>
- Hyndman, R.J., & Athanasopoulos, G. (2018). *Forecasting: Principles and Practice*, 2nd edition, OTexts: Melbourne, Australia. [OTexts.com/fpp2](https://www.otexts.com/fpp2).
- Islam, M. M., & Noor, F. A. (2022). Correlation between COVID-19 and weather variables: A meta-analysis. *Heliyon*, 8(8), e10333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e10333>
- Macusi, E. D., Rafon, J. K. A., & Macusi, E. S. (2022). Impact of COVID-19 and closed fishing season on commercial fishers of Davao Gulf, Mindanao, Philippines. *Ocean*

& Coastal Management, 217, 105997.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2021.105997>

Ospina, R., Gondim, J. a. M., Leiva, V., & Castro, C. (2023b). An Overview of Forecast Analysis with ARIMA Models during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Methodology and Case Study in Brazil. *Mathematics*, 11(14), 3069.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/math11143069>